

Understanding Riemann Hypothesis by Matrix-Graph Relation

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Abstract

Understanding Riemann Hypothesis could be possible by in extension of understanding Fermat's Last Theorem.

1 Understanding

By continuing preceding discussion in Fermat's Last Theorem [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Assuming that, } a^n + b^n = c^n \\ &\Rightarrow (\text{In matrix form of}) \ ((1 \times p) \cdot (p \times 1))^n + ((1 \times q) \cdot (q \times 1))^n = ((1 \times r) \cdot (r \times 1))^n \\ &\Rightarrow n^{(\max p)+(\max q)} = r^n \ (n \in \mathbf{N}^+) \Rightarrow n = 1 \text{ or } 2 \end{aligned}$$

This equation implies if any r ($r < c, r \in \mathbf{N}^+$) is given, there is always solution that fits a and b . In extension:

$$\begin{aligned} &((1 \times p) \cdot (p \times 1))^n + ((1 \times q) \cdot (q \times 1))^n = ((1 \times r) \cdot (r \times 1))^n \\ &\Rightarrow 2^{(\max p)+(\max q)} = r^n \end{aligned}$$

By giving condition of $1 \leq p \leq a, 1 \leq q \leq b$ in extension to $\mathbf{C}$ and a is conjugate complex number of b :

$$\begin{aligned} &a^n + b^n = c^n \Rightarrow 2^2 \leq c^2 \leq 2^{a+b} \Rightarrow 2^2 \leq (a^2 + b^2) \leq 2^{a+b} \\ &\implies 2 \leq \frac{a^2 + b^2}{2} \leq 2^{a+b-1} \end{aligned}$$

And definition of Riemann zeta function follows:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \dots$$

Riemann hypothesis statement asserts all the 'non-obvious' zeros of the zeta function are complex numbers with real part $1/2$ [1].

$$s = \frac{1}{2} + ki \ (k \in \mathbf{R}) \Rightarrow 0 = \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \dots$$

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By analytic approach, assuming sum in sequence of $x_{y+1} = x_y^{\log_y(y+1)}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{2^{a+b}} \leq \frac{1}{a^2+b^2} \leq \frac{1}{4} \\
& \left(\frac{1}{2^{a+b}}\right)^{\log_2 3} \leq \left(\frac{1}{a^2+b^2}\right)^{\log_2 3} \leq \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{\log_2 3} \\
& \dots \\
& \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^{a+b}} + \frac{1}{3^{a+b}} + \dots \leq 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{1}{a^2+b^2}\right)^{\log_2 3} + \left(\left(\frac{1}{a^2+b^2}\right)^{\log_2 3}\right)^{\log_3 4} + \dots \\
& \leq 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{\log_2 3} + \left(\frac{1}{9}\right)^{\log_3 4} + \dots \quad (\because a+b > 1) \\
& \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^{a+b}} + \frac{1}{3^{a+b}} + \dots \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\pi^2}{6} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-i \log(-1))^2}{6} \\
& \Rightarrow \zeta(a+b) \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-i \log(-1))^2}{6} \\
& \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{1}{c^2}\right)^{\log_2 3} + \left(\frac{1}{c^2}\right)^{\log_2 4} + \left(\frac{1}{c^2}\right)^{\log_2 5} + \dots \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-i \log(-1))^2}{6} \\
& \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^{\log_2 c} + \left(\frac{1}{1}\right)^{\log_2 c} + \left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^{\log_2 c} + \dots \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-i \log(-1))^2}{6} \\
& \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4^{\log_2 c}} (3^{\log_2 c} + 4^{\log_2 c} + 5^{\log_2 c} + \dots) \quad (\because a+b > 1) \\
& = \zeta(-\log_2 c) \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-i \log(-1))^2}{6} \\
& \Rightarrow a+b \leq \zeta^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-i \log(-1))^2}{6} \right) \leq \frac{1}{a^2+b^2} \\
& \Rightarrow \zeta \left(\frac{1}{a^2+b^2} \right) \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-i \log(-1))^2}{6} \leq \zeta(a+b) \\
& \Rightarrow \text{As keeping symmetry in } \zeta(x) = 0 \text{ function} \Rightarrow \Re(x) = \frac{1}{2}
\end{aligned}$$

References

- [1] BOMBIERI, E. Problems of the millennium: The Riemann hypothesis. *Clay Mathematics Institute* (2000).
- [2] YOON, J. Understanding Fermat's Last Theorem through Matrix-Graph Relation. Tech. rep., Zenodo, Dec. 2022.